

Studies on some Polynuclear Oxomolybdates

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The first triheteropoly complexes of molybdovanadophosphate were reported by Tsigdinos and Hallada¹. Kazanskii *et al.*² reported the solution phase studies of this class of compounds. Qureshi *et al.*³ studied the replacement of molybdenum by some transition metal atoms in 12-molybdosilicic acid, to form a mixed triheteropoly anion of the type $[\text{SiZMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}\text{H}_2]^{n-}$, where $Z = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} and Fe^{III} . Later a few alkali metal salts of the anion $[\text{SeMo}_{10}\text{V}_2\text{O}_{40}]^{6-}$ and some organic derivatives of $[\text{PMo}_{10}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_{40}]^{5-}$ have been prepared^{4,5}. Catalytic and industrial applications of some triheteropolymolybdates have also been reported⁵. Here we report isolation of a series of salts of two mixed triheteropoly anions, viz. $[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{10-}$ and $[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{10-}$.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the compounds are listed in Table 1. The final representation of the formulae followed the view and model established by Keggin⁵ for the 12-heteropoly anion $[\text{X}^n+\text{Mo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{-(8-n)}$.

The compounds have sharp ir bands at 790–860 (Mo–O–Mo bridging)⁷ and strong bands at 860–960 cm^{-1} (Mo–O). The bands of Mo–O and Mo–O–Mo are not distinguishable as they are absorbed nearly at the same region⁵. The sharp bands at 420–470 cm^{-1} are ascribed to tetrahedral⁸ Zn–O, which occupies the central tetrahedral site⁹ in each heteropoly cage. The medium intensity bands

at 415–450 cm^{-1} for the salts of $[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{10-}$ anion are assignable to octahedral Co–O linkages, whereas the bands at 1 490–1 590 cm^{-1} for the salts of heteropoly anion $[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{10-}$ are attributed to octahedral Ni–O which has replaced one MoO_6 addenda octahedra.

Thermal analyses of all the oxometallic salts showed characteristic endothermic peaks corresponding to dehydration. The first few large endothermic peaks below $150 \pm 20^\circ$ for all the salts, indicating the loss of water of crystallisation, are confirmed by the corresponding loss in weight of the compounds. On further increase in temperature, more endothermic peaks were found below 300° except $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4]_{10}[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].14\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which were found unstable above 280° and $[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4]_{10}[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which decomposed below 400° . The exothermic peaks at $350 \pm 50^\circ$ indicate the decomposition of the anionic cage which is confirmed by change in colour of the compound, whereas the sharp peaks even at higher temperature range followed by loss in weight of the compounds are due to the decomposition of higher metal oxides to the corresponding lower metal oxides, which are confirmed by total insolubility of the last residual product in water and elemental analyses. Ir spectra of the ignited samples at the decomposition temperature showed the absence of bands at 3 050–3 390, 1 600–1 640 and 580–680 cm^{-1} respectively, which are characteristic for water of crystallisation ($\nu_s + \nu_{\text{as}}$ OH lat-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF HETEROPOLY COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Cation	Co/Ni	Mo	Zn	H ₂ O
$\text{Na}_{10}[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].15\text{H}_2\text{O}$	9.05	2.71	46.12	2.42	12.10
	(9.91)	2.54	45.50	2.82	11.68)
$\text{K}_{10}[\text{ZnCbMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].10\text{H}_2\text{O}$	16.10	2.50	42.15	2.87	7.41
	(16.35)	2.46	44.14	2.73	7.53)
$[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4]_{10}[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].13\text{H}_2\text{O}$	25.1	2.4	35.25	2.21	8.71
	(26.49)	2.11	37.80	2.34	8.37)
$[\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4]_{10}[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].15\text{H}_2\text{O}$	37.27	2.02	29.67	2.02	8.20
	(38.35)	1.74	31.13	1.93	7.96)
$\text{Na}_{10}[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].23\text{H}_2\text{O}$	9.16	2.17	44.12	2.51	17.81
	(9.33)	2.38	42.84	2.65	16.81)
$\text{K}_{10}[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].13\text{H}_2\text{O}$	16.23	2.26	44.12	2.42	10.21
	(15.99)	2.41	43.17	2.67	9.57)
$[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4]_{10}[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].11\text{H}_2\text{O}$	27.12	2.06	39.14	2.14	6.97
	(26.84)	2.13	35.27	2.37	7.18)
$[\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4]_{10}[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}].14\text{H}_2\text{O}$	38.12	1.61	32.12	1.87	7.14
	38.54	1.74	31.31	1.94	7.47)

tice water), bending mode of lattice water and vibrational mode of constitutional water respectively.

The apparent molecular weights of the sodium salts of $[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{10-}$ and $[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}]^{10-}$ anions determined cryoscopically¹⁰ (taking 0.4 g salt using $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -water system as solvent), were found to be 2300 ± 20 and 2470 ± 20 against theoretical values of 2319.54 and 2463.32 respectively. The X-ray crystal data for $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{ZnCoMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were : $a = 17.61 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 15.21 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.87 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, system-orthorhombic, $Z = 2$, $V = 3715.05 \text{ \AA}^3$, $D_m = 2.0661 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$, and for $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{ZnNiMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were : $a = b = c = 15.862 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $Z = 2$, $V = 3990.92 \text{ \AA}^3$, $D_m = 2.042 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$ system-cubic. The observed data reveal molecular weights of the compounds to be 2312 and 2455 respectively.

Experimental

Sodium 11-molybdocobaltozincate(II) : An aqueous solution (50 ml) containing potassium acetate (30 g) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was added to an aqueous solution (100 ml) of sodium molybdate (6.6 g) at $50-60^\circ$. The mixture was treated with aqueous solution (50 ml) of zinc chloride (0.33 g) with vigorous stirring for 0.5 h on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was then ice-cooled and cobalt nitrate (0.7 g) in water (50 ml) was added to it followed by addition of acetic acid to adjust the pH at 4.13. It was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere at $80 \pm 5^\circ$ for about 4 h, then concentrated to two-third of the original volume, filtered and the filtrate was referigenerated overnight (5°). Light pink crystals that separated were crystallised from water.

The potassium salt of the heteropoly anion was prepared by metathetical reaction with sodium salt. Aqueous (10%) solution (10 ml) of Na_2CO_3 was added to lukewarm aqueous solution (100 ml) of sodium 11-molybdocobaltozincate (3.5 g). The reaction mixture was digested on a water-bath for 90 min and referigenerated overnight. Light brown powder that separated was air-dried.

The tetramethylammonium and tetraethylammonium salts of the heteropoly anion were prepared by treatment of tetramethylammonium chloride and tetraethylammonium chloride respectively, with sodium salt of the heteropoly anion by similar method adopted in case of potassium salt above.

Sodium 11-molybdonickelozincate(II) : To a mixture of glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and aqueous solution (50 ml) of zinc chloride (0.33 g) were added aqueous solution (50 ml) of nickel chloride (0.58 g) and aqueous solution (100 ml)

of sodium molybdate (6.08 g) and the mixture was stirred vigorously. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.27 by adding acetic acid and it was refluxed for 150 min. The reaction mixtures was reduced to 50 ml by digesting it over a water-bath and then set aside. Greenish blue crystals that appeared after 3 days were washed with n-hexane.

Potassium, tetramethylammonium and tetraethylammonium salts of this anion were prepared by metathesis following the procedure as described for the preparation of the cobaltozincate.

Sodium and potassium were estimated by flame photometry. Mo, Zn, Co and Ni were estimated on an ARL 3410 (Switzerland) inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrophotometer (ICPAES). C, H and N were estimated using a Coleman analyser. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. DTA and TGA experiments were performed at a heating rate of 5° min^{-1} using a STA 409 (Netzsch, Germany) analyser. X-Ray diffraction data were recorded on an Unicam-Weissenberg instrument. Molecular weights of the sodium salts were determined by depression of the transition points of the system $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

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References

1. G. A. TSGIDINOS and C. J. HALLADA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 437; T. J. R. WEAKLEY, *Struct. Bonding*, 1974, 18, 131.
2. L. P. KAZANSKII, V. M. CHAUVEAU and V. SPITSYN, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1976, 2, 256.
3. A. M. QURESHI, S. A. ZUBAIRI and S. A. MALIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, 38, 879.
4. G. M. MARCU and L. GHIZDAVU, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1976, 4, 21.
5. M. T. POPE, "Heteropoly and Isopoly Oxometallates", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1983.
6. E. M. McCARRON, H. STALEY and A. W. SLEIGHT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, 23, 1043; E. M. McCARRON and A. W. SLEIGHT, *Polyhedron*, 1986, 5, 129.
7. G. A. TSGIDINOS, "Heteropoly Compounds, Methodicum Chemicum", Academic, New York, 1976, Vol. 8, p 54.
8. J. VAN DER ELŠKEN and D. W. ROBINSON, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1961, 17, 1249.
9. S. K. ROY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 14, 694; 1977, 15, 358.
10. E. THILO and G. KRUGER, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1957, 61, 24